

Development of students' mobile planner application

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Abstract

The pandemic and digital technologies have changed and affected people's lives in all aspects, one of which is education. It has also affected how students spend their time, whether it is to efficiently do work and boost productivity or spend time online for recreation. The main objective of this study is to develop a mobile application designed to function as a student planner. The application aims to provide students with a user-friendly and efficient platform to plan, organize, and manage their tasks, schedules, and upcoming events. The application features include a dashboard that displays the user's current schedule, a calendar view that enables the scheduling and creation of events, and a reminder system that sends alerts for upcoming events. The application also allows students to list tasks, including a reminder system. Additionally, the application connects students and instructors for upcoming announcements. The application aims to enhance the productivity and organization of students, thereby improving their academic performance and time-management skills. To gather data, the application was evaluated by 100 participants, 80 End Users and 20 Expert Users using the ISO 9126 evaluation for software. The application was deemed highly acceptable by end-users and experts regarding usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability. Functionality received the highest average rating from end-users and specialists, 4.66, while efficiency received the lowest average rating, 4.49. Overall, the application scored 4.58, suggesting that it is a highly acceptable and functional tool for its intended purpose. The study concludes that the developed mobile planner application is a beneficial tool to help students and others improve their time management skills. The study's findings imply that the application may satisfy its users' needs and expectations and contribute to their success.

Keywords: *Student planner; Time management; Time management tools; Mobile application; Productivity.*

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Introduction

The pandemic has dramatically affected the lives of many, livelihoods, education, and day-to-day activities. Because of these changes, many people struggle to adapt or cope with these changes (Coles et al., 2022). The problem in today's generation is how people will overcome the rising challenges, which include students in higher education. Upon entering higher education, researchers believed that most students tend to be unprepared for independent, self-directed learning (Fathi, 2019).

To adapt to the changes, most people use certain technologies to efficiently do their work as it is useful (Daghan, 2017). Our lives, education, and workplace have dramatically transformed thanks to digital tools like cell phones, computers, and online collaboration software (later referred to as "apps") like Google Docs, Google Forms, and Microsoft Teams. In accordance with Berthon et al. (2019), people play games, utilize social media, study and work on them, and go to bed with them. In human history, digital tools and apps have permeated every aspect of our lives. Thanks to digital technologies and telework, people have more power over when, where, and what they do, but freedom and autonomy have a price. People frequently believe that new technology increases work productivity and frees up more time for recreation. Instead of being helpful, sometimes it hinders individuals from managing their time correctly towards a more necessary cause.

One of the solutions that society has adopted is time management skills (Alyami et al., 2021). Time management includes activities such as creating checklists or to-do lists for today or tomorrow. The importance of time management is also backed up by several studies that explored the relevance of time management strategies to improving academic time management and academic self-efficacy of students (Çevik, 2021; Irwansyah & Asrida, 2021; Irwansyah et al., 2021) and the association of time management in teaching performance (Olivo, 2021; Sahito & Vaisanen, 2017). Granted that the latter is not about students, however, this still proves that time management is essential to our lives and thus can be applied in learning.

Another solution prevalent in our society is using time management tools such as notification systems from people's daily used devices (Morrison et al., 2017) and time trackers (Kos, 2020; Sorokina et al., 2020). A notification system is a collection of protocols and procedures that may include human and computer elements. These systems are designed to generate and distribute timely communications to a single person or group. Simple notification systems rely on a single mode of communication, such as email or short message service (SMS).

A non-congested channel of notification system, like a Short Message Service, is more effective than congested channels such as Social Network Service (Mihci & Donmez, 2017). This led the researchers to wonder if the concept of time management skills with the use of time management tools together with a non-congested channel of notification system, e.g., an exclusive application for school schedules, is an effective way to communicate updates and notices to the students utilizing the application. People might say that students should be responsible, but with the pandemic, many people do not have the same privileges. What might seem easy for some students might be challenging for others (Özüdoğru, 2021). Therefore, the researchers will create a Student Planner Mobile Application System wherein the app will notify the students of their schedule with alarm sounds and has customizable features such as class schedule, to-do list, and study timer. By providing a non-congested channel of notification system, the students can focus on class schedule notifications more than other notifications, such as activity and announcements from a Learning Management System used by the student's respective school.

Another factor that mobile applications need to be useful for everyday use, especially for learning purposes, is their accessibility through online mode (Yen et al., 2018; Jiang et al., 2021). Content within online apps can be easily modified for use on different platforms, such as smartphones. Due to the ability to customize how information is presented, this feature makes the program easy to use and enjoyable. Online programs are more straightforward to customize than typical desktop applications. Software that runs on the web may also be adaptable to browser changes. This encourages mobile working and guarantees that users always have access to the necessary software (Khamooshi, 2019).

Learning analytics that track a student’s list of tasks and accomplishment helps them be motivated about their personal achievement. Achievement motivation energizes and directs behavior toward achievement and therefore is known to be an important determinant of academic success (Steinmayr et al., 2019). Making the mobile planner application exclusive for Dominican Students has its benefits. Exclusivity elicits many other psychological rewards including a sense of belonging and importance (Sukhraj, 2017). While there is a possibility of the mobile application being used by different institutions or barangays, we notice that students at St. Dominic College should definitely need to develop time management skills. With the information mentioned above, undeniably, the lack of resources and little time management has affected the student’s performance. Knowing that only some students have the same privileges, this research study aims to develop a student planner mobile application system that could help students improve their performance at school.

Objectives of the Study

The study’s objective is to develop a student violation management system for St. Dominic College of Asia in a web-based nature. The study specifically aims to:

1. Plan the flow of the project and regulate possible solutions to improve the processes involved in the previously proposed system.
2. Gather all the needed information and analyze the requirements for the design, development, and execution of the web-based student violation management system.
3. Design and develop appropriate functions, modules, and sub-modules that will serve as an alternative solution for the manual processing of recording and managing violations committed by the college students and application of corresponding sanctions.
4. Test and evaluate the system using the ISO 9126 International Standards to ensure that the project meets the requirements in the context of functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability before the deployment and implementation.
5. Provide a trusted, fully functional, and responsive web-based student violation management system for St. Dominic College of Asia.

Methodology

Agile Methodology

Figure 1. Agile Methodology

Figure 1 shows the detailed step-by-step process of the Development of Student Planner Mobile Application System. The following is a discussion of the phases of developing the project and an explanation of its steps.

Plan. The first phase of Agile Methodology is where the research brainstorming happens. The researchers came up with the idea to develop a student mobile planner application as an alternative solution for the students' time-management problems. Thus, the researchers started the planning phase by collecting all the information and requirements needed for the system. In this data gathering, the researchers will be able to know the path that they are taking. After collecting data, the researchers will choose the most suitable programming language to create the said system.

Design. The second phase of Agile Methodology is understanding and analyzing the data gathered. This is where the process of designing the program's actual appearance takes place. First, the researchers will gather the necessary tools and resources before starting the design phase. Then, the researchers will tackle the program's design from start to finish and will jot down what should be included and should not be. Regular maintenance will help to ensure that all requirements are built into the design process.

Code & Test. The third phase of Agile Methodology is where the coding process of the program happens. The researchers will focus on the design features of the system and its functions. This phase also involves a series of testing and documentation of results to resolve any flaws, errors, and bugs to improve and enhance the system processes. The researchers will also check how the program performs and if it is suitable to various device platforms and browsers for ease of access and control and delivers a better user experience.

Release. The fourth phase of Agile Methodology is to present the fully functional Students' Mobile Planner Application, evaluated and approved by the end-users and expert-users for utilization and will serve as an alternative solution for students' time-management problem. The researchers will release the system, ensure the delivery of high-quality solutions, and guaranteeing its working state.

Feedback. The fifth phase of Agile Methodology is where the users use the system. The researchers may monitor the working state of the implemented system by requiring feedback from users, to determine possible functions and modules to add for future updates and enhancements.

Feasibility Study

The Information, Communication, and Technology Office have approved the development of students' mobile planner application for St. Dominic College of Asia for the execution and implementation of the class schedules, to-do list, calendar, and study timer by creating a student planner aligned within the database of the institution. The system's features and design are suitable for operations to provide the best user experience. The proponents used Visual Studio Code to implement the code for the system, Java and PHP, to make the application or system development work properly and efficiently on any platform or language. The proponents also used Android Studio to create the mobile application and design a compelling UI. CodeIgniter is also used for the web part of the system. HeidiSql is also used for the system's database to keep a large amount of needed data.

System Analysis

The researchers did a performance testing of the Student Planner Mobile Application System. The researchers tested the program to discover its functionality in the testing. The program's performance will be evaluated using a Likert Scale on a survey questionnaire. The participants would choose between 1 and 5, with five being the highest, verbally interpreted as strongly agree, and one being the lowest, which means strongly disagree.

The respondents of the study consist of higher education students from St. Dominic College of Asia that would use the Dominican Planner as end-users and IT experts that would test and review the Dominican Planner and give feedback as expert users. 100 respondents participated in the project, with 80% end-users (n=80) and 20% experts (n=20). Presented are the factors to be considered.

1. **Functionality.** This will test the software's usefulness. It will try its suitability, accurateness, interoperability, compliance, and security.
2. **Usability.** This will assess the software's practicality. It will test its understandability, learnability, and operability.
3. **Efficiency.** This will evaluate the software's effectiveness. It will test its time and resource behavior.
4. **Maintainability.** This will examine the software's maintenance. It will test its analyzability, changeability, stability, and testability.
5. **Portability.** This will analyze if users can use the software on different platforms. It will test its adaptability, installability, conformance, and replaceability.

Table 1. Likert Scale

Numerical Scale	Equivalent	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating
5	Strongly Agree	4.51-5.00	Highly Acceptable
4	Agree	3.51-4.50	Very Acceptable
3	Neutral	2.51-3.50	Acceptable
2	Disagree	1.51-2.50	Fairly Acceptable
1	Strongly Disagree	1.0-1.50	Not Acceptable

The researchers utilized a five-point Likert Scale in Table 1, from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree, to properly evaluate the application's level of satisfaction in terms of functionality, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability based on the respondents' evaluation and feedback. The numerical scale also indicates the level of satisfaction from highly acceptable to not acceptable. The overall rating of the development of student's mobile planner application is anticipated to be 2.51 or higher for the researchers to conclude that the project is feasible and acceptable.

Evaluation Procedure

A survey was conducted to evaluate the performance of the system. The study was assessed using the ISO 9126 evaluation instrument for software, using the following standards: functionality, usability, reliability, portability, efficiency, and maintainability. Each bar has a range of 1-5 sub-standards to be rated using the Likert Scale, wherein the participants choose between 1 to 5, with five being the highest and one being the lowest. The researchers used a rating scale to evaluate the results wherein the attained mean was associated with its corresponding verbal interpretation (as seen in Table 3.7 and Table 3.8 of the Testing Procedure). After the evaluation, the data collected were tallied and analyzed. The mean (X) describes the validity of the respondents' responses.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Evaluation of the application's functionality

End Users (n=80)			Expert Users (n=20)		
Functionality	Mean	Remarks	Functionality	Mean	Remarks
Suitability. The application allows you to save and manage tasks, events, schedules, and timer presets.	4.65	Highly Acceptable	Suitability. The application's functionalities process the user input accordingly.	4.75	Highly Acceptable
Accurateness. The application shows results according to the user's requirements.	4.61	Highly Acceptable	Accurateness. The application functions accurately in compliance to its purpose.	4.65	Highly Acceptable
Interoperability. The schedule of the student is automated accordingly and accurately.	4.60	Highly Acceptable	Interoperability. The data from the web application and mobile application is in sync.	4.80	Highly Acceptable
Compliance. The application has available reports. (e.g., analytics, list of events, list of tasks)	4.54	Highly Acceptable	Compliance. The application complies with the system's functionality standard (e.g., user credentials, reports)	4.65	Highly Acceptable
Security. The application requires the use of a strong password, such as a combination of alphabets and numbers.	4.64	Highly Acceptable	Security. The application utilizes encryption, such as HASH encryption, to protect user passwords.	4.65	Highly Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.61	Highly Acceptable		4.70	Highly Acceptable

Table 2 reveals the evaluation of the application's functionality. Based on the end-users' evaluation, the functionality of the application received a highly acceptable rating of 4.61. The application was evaluated on five different aspects of its functionality, including suitability, accuracy, interoperability, compliance, and security. The end-users found the application highly suitable for saving and managing tasks, events, schedules, and timer presets. The application also provided accurate results according to the user's requirements and automated the schedule of the student accordingly and accurately. The availability of reports, such as analytics, list of events, and list of tasks, was highly compliant with the end-users' expectations. The application's security was highly acceptable, as it required the use of a strong password to ensure account accessibility and security. Overall, the end-users' evaluation suggests that the application's functionality is highly satisfactory and meets their expectations.

On the other hand, based on the expert ratings, the application's functionality received a highly acceptable score of 4.7. The score indicates that the application's functionalities process the user input correctly, and the application functions accurately in compliance with its purpose. Additionally, the data from the web and mobile applications are in sync, and the application complies with the system's functionality standard, including user credentials and reports. The application also utilizes encryption, such as HASH encryption, to protect user passwords, ensuring security. The ratings suggest that the application's functionality is highly suitable, accurate, interoperable, compliant, and secure. Overall, the rating reflects the experts' positive evaluation of the application's functionality. Based on this assessment, users can rely on the application's functionalities to process their input accurately and securely, providing them with a satisfactory user experience.

Table 3 reveals the evaluation of the application's usability. The end-users' evaluation of the application's usability received a highly acceptable rating of 4.54. The usability of the application was evaluated based on three aspects, including understandability, learnability, and operability. The end-users found the application highly understandable, as it could be navigated easily, and provided easily understood error messages. The application's learnability was also highly acceptable, as it could be used easily without instructions. The operability of the application was highly satisfactory, as it handled user input efficiently. Overall, the end-users' evaluation suggests that the application's usability is highly acceptable, meeting their expectations for ease of navigation, user-friendliness, and proper processing of user inputs.

Table 3. Evaluation of the application's usability

End Users (n=80)			Expert Users (n=20)		
Usability	Mean	Remarks	Usability	Mean	Remarks
Understandability. The application can be navigated easily and provide easily understood error messages.	4.53	Highly Acceptable	Understandability. The application's function and visual aids are clear, complete, and accurate.	4.65	Highly Acceptable
Learnability. The application can be used easily without instructions.	4.49	Very Acceptable	Learnability. The application adapts to different user skill levels and learning styles.	4.6	Highly Acceptable
Operability. The application handles user input efficiently.	4.59	Highly Acceptable	Operability. The application easily recovers from system failures, errors, and crashes to minimize disruption to the user.	4.6	Highly Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.54	Highly Acceptable		4.62	Highly Acceptable

Based on the expert ratings, the application's usability received a highly acceptable score of 4.62. The score indicates that the application's function and visual aids are clear, complete, and accurate, making it easy for users to understand. The application also adapts to different user skill levels and learning styles, indicating its high learnability. Additionally, the application easily recovers from system failures, errors, and crashes, minimizing disruption to the user, indicating its high operability. The ratings suggest that the application's usability is highly understandable, learnable, and operable, providing users with an excellent user experience. Overall, the rating reflects the experts' positive evaluation of the application's usability. Based on this assessment, users can rely on the application's easy-to-understand user interface, ease of use, and recoverability to provide them with a satisfactory user experience.

Table 4. Evaluation of the application's efficiency

End Users (n=80)			Expert Users (n=20)		
Efficiency	Mean	Remarks	Efficiency	Mean	Remarks
Time behavior. The application provides minimal delay when using a function.	4.39	Very Acceptable	Time behavior. The application is very responsive to user input.	4.45	Very Acceptable
Resource behavior. The application loads easily when selecting different functions.	4.56	Highly Acceptable	Resource behavior. The application performs well with minimal specifications.	4.55	Highly Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.48	Very Acceptable		4.50	Highly Acceptable

Table 4 indicates the evaluation of the application's efficiency. The end-users' evaluation of the application's efficiency received a very acceptable rating of 4.48. The efficiency of the application was evaluated based on two aspects, including time behavior and resource behavior. The end-users found the application's time behavior to be very acceptable, as it provided minimal delay when using a function. The application's resource behavior was highly acceptable, as it loaded easily when selecting different functions. Overall, the end-users' evaluation suggests that the application's efficiency is very acceptable, meeting their expectations for responsiveness and processing speed of functions.

Based on the expert ratings, the application's efficiency received a very acceptable score of 4.50. The rating indicates that the application is very responsive to user input, indicating its high time behavior. Additionally, the application performs well with minimal specifications, indicating its high resource behavior. The ratings suggest that the application's efficiency is very acceptable, providing users with a fast and responsive user experience, even with minimal resources. Overall, the score reflects the experts' positive evaluation of the application's efficiency. Based on this assessment, users can rely on the application to perform well, even with minimal specifications, and provide them with a fast and responsive user experience.

Table 5. Evaluation of the application's maintainability

End Users (n=80)			Expert Users (n=20)		
Maintainability	Mean	Remarks	Maintainability	Mean	Remarks
Analyzability. The application has error messages that are easy to understand in case of failure.	4.39	Very Acceptable	Analyzability. The application failures are easy to diagnose.	4.70	Highly Acceptable
Changeability. The application is capable of running even after modifying application settings (e.g., toggling notifications, clear cache)	4.55	Highly Acceptable	Changeability. The application meets user needs and no major disruptions occur over time.	4.65	Highly Acceptable
Stability. The application does not become slower or less responsive over time during use.	4.48	Very Acceptable	Stability. The application does not encounter crashes or errors during heavy usage.	4.55	Highly Acceptable
Testability. The application's features and functionalities perform well during use.	4.68	Highly Acceptable	Testability. The application does not reproduce bugs or issues during testing.	4.65	Highly Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.53	Highly Acceptable		4.64	Highly Acceptable

Table 5 shows the evaluation of the application's maintainability. The end-users' evaluation of the application's maintainability received a highly acceptable rating of 4.53. The maintainability of the application was evaluated based on four aspects, including analyzability, changeability, stability, and testability. The end-users found the application's analyzability to be very acceptable, as it had error messages that were easy to understand in case of failure. The changeability of the application was highly acceptable, as it could run even after modifying application settings. The application's stability was also very acceptable, as it did not become slower or less responsive over time during use. The testability of the application was highly acceptable, as its features and functionalities performed well during use. Overall, the end-users' evaluation suggests that the application's maintainability is highly acceptable, meeting their expectations for visible error messages, tolerance, responsiveness over time, and functionalities during use.

Based on the expert ratings, the application's maintainability received a highly acceptable score of 4.64. The rating indicates that the application's failures are easy to diagnose, indicating its high analyzability. Additionally, the application meets user needs, and no major disruptions occur over time, indicating its high changeability. The application also does not encounter crashes or errors during heavy usage, indicating its high stability. Furthermore, the application does not reproduce bugs or issues during testing, indicating its high testability. The ratings suggest that the application's maintainability is highly acceptable, providing users with an error-free and consistent user experience over time. Overall, the rating reflects the experts' positive evaluation of the application's maintainability. Based on this assessment, users can rely on the application to provide a consistent user experience over time, with minimal interruptions and errors, making it easy to diagnose and fix issues.

Table 6 shows the evaluation of the application's portability. The end-users' evaluation of the application's portability received a highly acceptable rating of 4.59. The portability of the application was evaluated based on four aspects, including adaptability, installability, conformance, and replaceability. The end-users found the application's adaptability to be highly acceptable, as the users does not encounter compatibility issues with android versions 9 and up. The installability of the application was highly acceptable, as the users does not experience issues while installing application updates. The application's conformance was also highly acceptable, as it accurately retains the user's data when transferring to another device. The replaceability of the application was highly acceptable, as it does not encounter errors when transferring to a new device. Overall, the end-users' evaluation suggests that the application's portability is highly acceptable, meeting their expectations for compatibility with android versions 9 and up, ease of installation, retains user's data, and can be transferred to other devices.

Table 6. Evaluation of the application's portability

End Users (n=80)			Expert Users (n=20)		
Functionality	Mean	Remarks	Functionality	Mean	Remarks
Adaptability. The application does not experience compatibility issues with your current Android Version (9 and up).	4.61	Highly Acceptable	Adaptability. The application does not encounter any difficulties in adapting the project to different API levels (API level 28 and up).	4.5	Very Acceptable
Installability. The application does not experience issues while installing application updates or new version on your Android Device (Android Version 9 and up).	4.64	Highly Acceptable	Installability. The application does not encounter any errors or bugs during the installation process of a new android versions (API level 28 and up).	4.6	Highly Acceptable
Conformance. The application accurately retains your data when transferring to another device (e.g., logging onto a new mobile device)	4.56	Highly Acceptable	Conformance. The application conforms to portability standards. (e.g., obtain, move, copy, transfer and reuse personal data across different mobile devices)	4.6	Highly Acceptable
Replaceability. The application does not encounter errors when transferring to a new device.	4.56	Highly Acceptable	Replaceability. The application does not encounter compatibility issues when ensuring the replaceability application process.	4.65	Highly Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.59	Highly Acceptable		4.59	Highly Acceptable

Based on the expert ratings, the application's portability received a highly acceptable score of 4.59. The rating indicates that the application is compatible with different API levels from 28 and up, indicating its high adaptability. Additionally, the application can be installed easily, indicating its high installability. The application meets the standards for obtaining, moving, copying, transferring, and reusing personal data across different mobile devices., indicating its high conformance. Furthermore, the application does not encounter compatibility issues when ensuring the replaceability application process, indicating its high replaceability. The ratings suggest that the application's portability is highly acceptable in terms of compatibility across multiple Android versions and devices. Overall, the rating reflects the experts' positive evaluation of the application's portability. Based on this assessment, users can rely on the application to provide a versatile compatibility with different android versions and devices, making it a reliable and accessible tool for users.

Table 7. End-users and Experts' Overall Level of Satisfaction

Category	End-User	Experts	Overall Rating	Remarks
Functionality	4.61	4.70	4.66	Highly Acceptable
Usability	4.54	4.62	4.58	Highly Acceptable
Efficiency	4.48	4.50	4.49	Very Acceptable
Maintainability	4.53	4.64	4.59	Highly Acceptable
Portability	4.59	4.59	4.59	Highly Acceptable
Overall Average	4.55	4.61	4.58	Highly Acceptable

Table 7 identifies the end-users and experts' overall level of satisfaction. The data presented in the table shows the overall average rating for end-users which is 4.55, while the overall average rating for experts is slightly higher at 4.61, indicating that they are both highly satisfied with the application. The combined overall average rating of 4.58 suggests that the application is highly acceptable for both end-users and experts.

Both end-users and experts are highly satisfied with the application's functionality, usability, maintainability, and portability, with all categories receiving highly acceptable remarks. The application's efficiency was rated as very acceptable by both groups, indicating that it performs well, but may have some room for improvement. These results indicate that the application is meeting the needs and expectations of both groups, suggesting that it is well-designed and effective. Developers can use this feedback to continue to improve the application, ensuring that it remains effective and efficient for all users. Overall, the data suggests that the application is a success, and both end-users and experts are highly satisfied with its performance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study's findings show that the time management-focused mobile planner app for students has successfully complied with ISO 9126 requirements. It has received high ratings for usability, functionality, efficiency, maintainability, and portability from both end users and industry professionals. The application is acceptable, accurate, secure, user-friendly, and capable of correctly processing user inputs. The mobile time management app has much potential because its features can be used in different environments other than schools. It is helpful for those people who want to improve their time management skills and to be more productive in a day. Also, they can track their individual performance through analytics, and by that, it will keep them improving to become better students.

The researchers were able to develop a student mobile planner application which resolves certain issues and problems, and with the data gathered and analysis accomplished. Thus, the researchers conclude that by giving the SDCA students from higher education an application that will remind them about their class schedule. Students will not forget their schedule, and the application will ensure that important schedules are reminded to them. Student responsibilities are constantly reminded of. The To-Do list created by the students is now organized for them, resulting into an easily manageable task. If ever they forget their important tasks, they will be notified about it.

With the calendar module, the deans, program chairs, and instructors can now easily announce important matters to their students who has the mobile application, and students will be reminded of the announcement ahead of time. While the study timer module allows students to keep track of time in doing various activities.

The overall level of satisfaction in the context of Functionality, Usability, Efficiency, Maintainability, and Portability of the application is considered highly acceptable, according to the results gathered from the respondents using the ISO 9126 evaluation for software. Therefore, the application is fit for deployment and implementation.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following are the recommendations suggested for future researchers:

1. Use a framework that can cater to both IOS and Android Devices.
2. Include a widget option that can easily access essential information.
3. Integrate the mobile phone's alarm for the notification system.
4. Customizable themes for the application.
5. Utilize the application in terms of its availability to other institutions.

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